

Research Article

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DISTRIBUTION AND RISK ASSESSMENTS OF HEXACHLOROCYCLOHEXANES (HCHs) AND ENDOSULFANS IN WATER, SEDIMENTS AND FISH FROM HAWUL RIVER BASIN, NORTH-EAST NIGERIA

¹Abubakar Umar Dewa, ²Baba Nwunuji Hikon, and ³Nelson Jonathan

¹Department of Chemical Sciences, Federal University of Kashere, Gombe, PMB 0182, Gombe, Gombe State, Nigeria.

²Department of Chemical Sciences, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria.

³Department of Chemistry, Adamawa State College of Education, Hong, PMB 2237, Adamawa State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author's Email Address: umardewa@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Hexachlorocyclohexanes (HCHs) and endosulfans organochlorines were investigated to assess the levels of contamination in water, sediment and fish from River Hawul basin. Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged and Safe (QuEChERS) method was employed for the extraction and clean-up of the residues while GC-MS was used for identification and quantification of the pesticides residues. The concentration of HCHs in water from all the sampling locations are greater than the recommended maximum residues limit (MRL) value of 0.01 mg/L. This study reports α/γ ratio of 1 and below for all sampling sites indicating recent usage in the areas despite its ban. Endosulfan I and II are detected in all the samples from all sampling locations but their metabolite which is endosulfan sulphate was absent. Hazard Quotients (HQ) for the organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) in water are by far > 1 , indicating high probabilities of non-carcinogenic health hazards occurring in children due to consumption of the water from the sampling locations in the study area. The Hazard Index (HI) which is the cumulative effect of the individual OCPs is in the sequence Kopri $>$ Garkida (WB) $>$ Garkida $>$ Daba $>$ kiri $>$ Ndabna. β -HCH had the highest contribution to cancer risk in water with a range of $1.27 \times 10^{-1} - 5.28 \times 10^{-3}$. The incremental life time cancer risk ranges between $1.85 \times 10^{-1} - 4.09 \times 10^{-2}$. The incremental lifetime cancer risk for fish consumption ranges between $8.33 \times 10^{-4} - 3.32 \times 10^{-3}$ and $5.00 \times 10^{-3} - 1.99 \times 10^{-2}$ for an Adult and a child of 10Kg weight respectively.

Keyword: Hexachlorocyclohexanes (HCHs); Endosulfans; Organochlorines; QuEChERS

INTRODUCTION

The importance of pesticides in improving the quality of our daily life through ensuring food security and public health cannot be over emphasized, however, there are increasing concerns with regards to fate of this pesticides and their metabolites in the environment [1-4]

Bearing in mind the broad spectrum nature of pesticides and their potential to poison non-targets like humans, animals and aquatic life [5]. These concerns are genuine, since it is estimated only about 0.1- 0.3 % of the pesticides actually meet the target [6]. The remaining going into the environment with water bodies being the major reservoir and sink [7-8]. The accumulation of the remaining more than 99% of this pesticides in the environment, especially water and bottom sediments is a serious threat to the environment, human health and aquatic life due to their persistence, long range transport, bio magnification and toxicity even at low concentration [9-10].

Organochlorines are found to constitute over 40% of all the pesticides in use [11]. Organochlorines are organic molecule having the elements hydrogen, carbon, chlorine, and occasionally oxygen and sulphur. It has covalent bonds formed when its electron pairs share space with one or more chlorine atoms. Ogunfowokan *et al.* [12] state that dichlorodiphenylethanes, cyclodienes, or chlorinated benzenes are examples of synthetic, non-polar, toxic, and environmentally persistent pesticides.

OCPs have the ability to volatilize and travel great distances from where they were initially applied through the atmosphere to become deposited in remote regions, and also have the ability to bioaccumulate and biomagnify, and can bioconcentrate up to 70,000 times their original concentrations [13 - 14]. OCPs are lipophilic contact insecticides; they have low vapour pressures and slow rates of environmental degradation [15]. These properties make them highly penetrable, long lasting, and extremely effective pesticide agents [16]. They are also among the twelve chemical substances called "dirty dozen" and defined under the Stockholm Convention [17-18].

Hexachlorocyclohexanes (HCHs) and Endosulfan I and II are some of the widely used pesticides which are banned under the Stockholm Convention. The alpha and beta isomers of HCHs are included in the priority list of persistent organic pollutants by the Stockholm convention 2009 [19]. Technical grade HCH contain 10-15 % γ -HCH as well as other isomers in different proportions [20]. γ - HCH, commonly called lindane is produced and used as an insecticide on fruit, vegetables, and forest crops. It is a white solid that may evaporate into the air as a colorless vapor with a slightly musty odor.

The HCHs are regarded as possible carcinogens and endocrine disruptors with proven teratogenic, mutagenic and genotoxic effects which lead to their ban in 52 countries and restriction in 33 others [21].

Chemically related to DDT, Endosulfan became a widely used pesticide in agriculture and related industries to combat a variety of insects and mites. The biologically active isomers α -endosulfan and

β -endosulfan, along with some impurities, are combined in a diastereomeric mixture known as the technical grade of endosulfan in a 7:3 ratio [22-23].

Despite the phase out of the production and distribution of all the isomers of HCH and endosulfan they continue to be detected in air, soil and water bodies around the world, even at the arctic, this further prove their persistence, long range transport capabilities, bioaccumulation and can cause adverse effect such as cancers, birth defects and even deaths in both human and animals [10].

River Hawul basin is one of the most important river basins in north east Nigeria whose inhabitants are mostly subsistence and commercial farmers [24]. This river basin serves as source of livelihood to majority of the populace that live along the river. It provides food such as fish and other aquatic animals and plants, serves as source of drinking water, water for irrigation and sports (swimming). Therefore, there is a need to study the water body and determine the levels of these environmental pollutants.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area and Sampling

The Study area lies between longitudes 11.00°N and 10.00°N and Latitude 12.00°E to 13.00° E (figure 1). The sample collection locations were Kopri (10° 28'2''N, 12°50'49''E) Ndabna (10° 23'2''N, 12°49'27''E) in Hong L.G.A, Garkida WB (10° 24'52''N, 12°33'58''E) Garkida (10° 24'52''N, 12°33'58''E) in Gombi L.G.A, Kiri (9° 35'41'' N, 12°00'05'' E) and Daba (9° 40'0''N, 12°10'59''E) in Shelleng L.G.A. The sampling locations are steep part of the basin which receive their waters from the flood plains of the Hawul basin and keeps them throughout the year. The important human activities around the sampling areas are irrigation farming, fishing, washing, swimming during the day and some pockets of illegal artisanal mining.

Figure 1: Map of the study area sourced from Mayomi *et al.* [24]

Sample Collection

The study area was divided into six sampling sites along the Adamawa part of Hawul River Basin in which samples of water, sediments and fish were collected. Each sample was taken in triplicate from which representative samples were drawn from.

Water Sampling

A total volume of 1 L water sample was collected as reported by Olawale *et al.* [25] from each site in polyethylene bottles (twice rinsed with deionized water) and acidified with 3% HNO₃ then stored in an ice box and transported to the laboratory for further analysis. Each sample was taken in triplicate from which a representative sample was drawn from.

Sediments Sampling

A total of 50 g of sediment samples, from a depth of 2-5 cm under the riverbed was collected. The sediment samples were dried in a laboratory for about 48 h at 120 °C and then homogenized by grinding in an agate mortar and sieved. It was stored in labelled bottles until chemical analysis.

Fish Sampling

Live sample of African Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) was caught from the sampling points with the help of a local fisherman [25]. The fish samples were sacrificed, briefly rinsed with distilled water to remove any adhering substances then immediately preserved on ice in an ice box then deep frozen in the laboratory before analysis. After identification, the fish samples were dissected into separate organs: flesh, liver, and gills using stainless steel and then air dried to constant weight.

Determination of OCPs Concentrations

The QuEChERS method for pesticide analysis according to EPA methods was adopted as reported by Akoto *et al.* [26] and Modibbo *et al.* [27] with slight modification in terms of sample size for all samples.

Extraction of Pesticide Residues in Water

Fifty (50) mL of dichloromethane (DCM) was introduced into a separating funnel containing 100 mL of the water sample and shaken vigorously for 5 minutes [28]. The sample was allowed to settle for 30 minutes to facilitate effective separation of the organic and aqueous phases. After separation, the organic layer was filtered into a 250 mL volumetric flask through anhydrous sodium sulphate (Na₂SO₄) that has been prewashed with DCM. The extraction was repeated twice using 50 mL of dichloromethane (DCM) [29]. The extracts were then combined and dried by passing through a glass funnel packed with activated anhydrous sodium sulphate (Na₂SO₄). The extracts were concentrated to 5 mL using a rotary evaporator at a temperature of 45°C. The level of organochlorine pesticide residues in the water samples was determined using gas chromatography coupled with a mass spectrometer (GC-MS).

Extraction of Pesticide Residues in Sediments

A 10.0 g dry sediment sample was transferred into an extraction thimble that was previously washed with *n*-hexane and acetone and was oven dried. Pesticide residues in sediments was extracted using 150 mL of *n*-hexane/acetone mixture 4:1 v/v for 6 h by soxhlet extraction. The extract was concentrated to near dryness using vacuum rotary evaporator at 40 °C. Each extract was then dissolved in 10 mL of *n*-hexane and subjected to clean-up. Concentration levels of the pesticide residues were determined using GC-MS [29].

Extraction of Pesticide Residues in Fish

Ten (10.0) g of homogenized fish sample was placed into a 100 mL conical flask and 20.0 g of activated anhydrous sodium sulphate was added and mixed [29]. Then 30 mL of 2:1(v/v) hexane/acetone mixture was added and thoroughly mixed by shaking. The sample was then be sonicated for 20 min. The supernatant was filtered into a 250 mL round bottom flask. The extraction was repeated two more times and all the supernatants was combined and concentrated at 40 °C to near dryness using a rotary evaporator.

Sample Clean - up

Octadecyl (C18) modified silica gel (2.5 g) was weighed and parked into a glass column which has been plugged with glass wool and 1.0 g of anhydrous sodium sulphate [29]. Ten (10) mL *n*-hexane was used to wet and rinse the column. The extract was then transferred into a column and eluted with 20 mL portions of hexane/acetone mixtures. The eluents were collected into a round bottomed flask and then concentrated to dryness. The residues were then dissolved in 2 mL of ethyl acetate and placed in a GC vial for gas chromatograph analysis.

Health Risk Estimation due to OCPs

The non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic health risk estimates for each of the organochlorine pesticides residues in water and fish was computed using basic standard indices: The Estimated Average Daily Intake (EDI), Average Daily Intake (mg/ kg/d), Hazard Quotients, the Hazard Index (HI) and cancer risk as reported by Akoto *et al.* [26], Adeleye *et al.* [30]. Water and fish consumption rate of 2.2 L/day and 13.3 Kg/year were adopted as reported by Zakir *et al.* [31] and Bradley *et al.* [32].

$$\text{EADI} = \frac{\text{Mean residual pesticide concentration (mg/ kg)} \times \text{food consumption rate (kg /day)}}{\text{Mean body weight (Kg)}}$$

$$\text{Hazard Quotients (HQ)} = \frac{\text{Estimated Average Daily Intake (EADI)}}{\text{Average Daily Intake (mg/kg/d)}}$$

$$\text{Hazard Index (HI)} = \sum \frac{\text{Estimated Average Daily Intake (EADI)}}{\text{Average Daily Intake (mg/kg/d)}}$$

When the health risk index is > 1 , the food involved is considered a risk to the consumers; when the index < 1 , the food involved is considered acceptable.

Cancer risk = EDI x Cancer slope Factor (CSF)

Table 1: Constants adopted for estimation of Health risk index for OCPs

Compound	CSF ingestion (1/(mg/kg/d))	MRL(mg/Kg)	ADI(mg/KgBW)	Reference
α -HCH	6.30E+00	0.01	0.005	[33]
β -HCH	1.80E+00	0.01	0.005	Ibid.
γ -HCH	1.30E+00	0.01	0.005	Ibid.
δ -HCH	1.80E+00	0.01	0.005	Ibid.
Endosulfan I	NC	0.2	0.006	Ibid.
Endosulfan II	NC	0.2	0.006	Ibid.

NC = non-carcinogenic

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Concentration Level of Organochlorines in Water Samples

Table 2 shows the concentration of organochlorines in water samples (mg/L). The concentration of HCHs in water from all the sampling locations are greater than the recommended MRL value of 0.01 mg/L [34]. HCH being a broad spectrum pesticide for an agricultural purpose is widely used by farmers under various market names. Technical HCH consists of four isomers α -HCH (60-70 %), β -HCH (5-12 %), γ -HCH (10-15%), and δ -HCH (6-10 %), while HCH contains $> 90\%$ of γ -HCH. All the four isomers were detected in all water samples with β -HCH being the most abundant of the four. This can be attributed to the assertion that β -HCH is the most stable and relatively resistant to microbial degradation owing to the special arrangement of chlorine atoms in the molecular structure of β -HCH [35].

The source apportionment of all the four HCH isomers is based on α/γ ratio which is used to identify the possible HCH age in the environment [36-37]. The ratio of α -HCH to γ -HCH greater than 3 indicates an input of technical HCH and long-range atmospheric transport and deposition. However, a ratio close to or < 1 is characteristic of HCH sources [38]. This study reports α/γ ratio of 1 and below for all sampling sites. This indicates that, there is possibility of HCH still recently being use in the areas despite its ban by NAFDAC in Nigeria.

Endosulfan I and endosulfan II isomers are also referred to as α and β endosulfan. Technical endosulfan compose of diastereomeric mixture of α -endosulfan and β -endosulfan in 7:3 [22]. Both isomers were present in all the samples from all sampling locations but their metabolite which is endosulfan sulphate was absent. Both isomers are fairly resistant to photo degradation unlike their metabolite which is susceptible to photo degradation [39]. The ratio of endosulfan I /endosulfan II < 2.33 is used in source apportionment of endosulfan in the environment. In this work, the ratio of endosulfan I / endosulfan II in water is less 1 implying none usage of technical endosulfan recently in the study area.

Table 2: Concentration of organochlorines in water samples (mg/L)

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	(WB)	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α - HCH	0.15	0.13	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.05
β - HCH	1.93	0.08	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.38
δ - HCH	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.05
γ - HCH	0.43	0.09	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.16
Endosulfan I	0.61	0.46	0.22	0.015	0.08	0.3
Endosulfan II	1.13	1	1.69	0.27	0.3	0.29

Concentration Levels of Organochlorines in Sediment Samples

Table 3 shows the concentration levels of organochlorines residues in sediment samples. All the four isomers of HCHs were detected in all the sediment sample from the study areas with β -HCH being the most abundant of the four isomers in the sampling location except in Garkida (WB) where it was less than the α and δ isomers. This can be attributed to the likelihood of conversion of the α -HCH and γ -HCH isomers to β -HCH. Secondly, it may due to the special conformation exhibited by β -HCH which makes it difficult to undergo microbial degradation.

The ratio of α -HCH to γ -HCH which is the basis for source apportionment of HCHs in the environment are higher than that those of the water samples from all sampling location but still less 3. This is an indication of continuous use of HCH in the study areas. The half-life of these HCHs being 15 months, 50 days and 20 days for α -HCH, γ -HCH and β -HCH (WHO), and the high concentration in the sediment samples can be a further confirmation of recent use of HCH in the sampling locations.

This finding is in agreement with the report of Unyimadu *et al.* [40] where he observed a similar trend with Gurara 1, 2, Brass 11, 12 and Nicholas 14, 15.

Endosulfan I and II were also detected in all the sediments samples with endosulfan II being more abundant. Their metabolite, endosulfan sulphate was not detected in all the sampling locations. The

sequence of Endosulfans in the sediments is Ndabna > Kiri > Garkida WB > Garkida > Daba > Kopri. Similarly, the ratio of endosulfan I/II is less than 2.33 in all the sampling locations indicating none application of technical endosulfan and confirmation of its persistence in environmental compartments [22].

Table 3: Concentration of Organochlorines in Sediments (mg/kg)

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	(WB)	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α - HCH	0.09	0.09	1.11	0.04	0.08	0.11
β - HCH	0.13	0.17	0.45	0.21	0.2	0.11
δ - HCH	0.05	0.02	0.7	0.07	0.05	0.08
γ - HCH	0.04	0.07	0.4	0.07	0.14	0.04
Endosulfan I	0.18	0.22	0.78	0.21	0.09	0.04
Endosulfan II	0.42	0.22	0.95	0.57	0.47	0.46

Concentration Levels of Organochlorines in Fish Samples

From Table 4 it can be seen that all the four isomers of HCH are detected in fish samples from all the sampling locations with β -HCH recording the highest concentration. The concentration of the HCHs ranges between 0.08 mg/kg – 0.2 mg/kg for α -HCH, 0.09 mg/kg - 2.37 mg/kg for β -HCH, 0.03 mg/kg – 0.1 mg/kg for δ -HCH while that of γ -HCH is 0.1mg/kg - 0.4mg/kg. the special conformation exhibited by β -HCH which makes highly stable or resistance to microbial degradation and the conversion of the α -HCH and γ -HCH isomers to β -HCH may be responsible for the high concentration of the β -HCH observed.

The ratio of α -HCH to γ -HCH is often considered the characteristic index to determination of source apportionment of the HCHs. In this study, the α -HCH/ γ -HCH is less than 1 for all sampling location except Kiri which has a ratio of 2, this points to a possible use of HCH in the vicinity of the sampling locations.

Both endosulfan I and II were detected in 100 % of the samples with a range of 0.18 mg/kg - 5.76 mg/kg for endonsulfan I and 0.54mg/Kg - 1.61mg/kg for endosulfan II

Endosulfan classified as a ‘Moderately Hazardous’ chemical by WHO (Class-II) are known to be very toxic to aquatic animals which negatively affect fish reproduction and may even lead to fish kills [41]. This may be the reason of lack of some species of fish and the depletion of the fish population. The ratio of endosulfan I to endosulfan II for all samples from the sampling location are less than 2.33, this indicates aged usage of endosulfan and its ability to bioaccumulate in fish due to their lipophilic nature.

Table 4: Concentration of organochlorines in fish samples (mg/kg)

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	(WB)	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α - HCH	0.15	0.11	0.15	0.15	0.08	0.2
β - HCH	1.03	2.37	1.93	0.09	0.45	1.06
δ - HCH	0.1	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.06	0.04
γ - HCH	0.4	0.3	0.43	0.16	0.17	0.1
Endosulfan I	0.74	5.76	0.61	0.18	0.87	2.93
Endosulfan II	1.27	1.61	1.13	0.54	0.89	0.93

Health Risk Estimation

Health risk associated with the consumption of water and fish from all sampling locations in this study were computed to assess the probability of adverse effect or otherwise due to presence of OCPs analysed. The carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risks were estimated using hazard quotients and cancer risks by adopting the United States Environmental Protection Agency [42] protocol as reported by Akoto *et al.* [26] and Adeleye *et al.* [30].

Non-Carcinogenic Health Risk Hazards in Water

The non-carcinogenic health risk hazards were measured by computing the estimated daily intake (EDI) due to ingestion of water and fish which in turn were used to calculate the Hazard quotient (HQ) and Hazard index (HI). The computed HQ for the respective OCPs in water are presented in tables 5, 6 and 7. From table 5 it can also be seen the Hazard Quotients for the OCPs are by far > 1 , indicating high probabilities of non-carcinogenic health hazards occurring in children due to consumption of the waters from the sampling locations in the study area.

It can also be observed that the Hazard quotients decreases with increase in body weight. This means people of lower body weight (especially children) will be more susceptible to health Hazard pose by these OCPs in water than those with higher body weight. The HI which is the cumulative effect of the individual OCPs is in the sequence Kopri $>$ Garkida (WB) $>$ Garkida $>$ Daba $>$ kiri $>$ Ndabna. This simply implies people in Kopri may experience more health hazard due water ingestion than other sampling locations.

Table 5: Hazard Quotient (EDI/ADI) due water ingestion for children (10 Kg)

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	WB	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α -HCH	6.6000	5.7200	2.2000	1.7600	0.8800	55.00
β -HCH	84.9200	3.5200	6.1600	6.1600	5.7200	418.00
δ -HCH	1.7600	0.8800	0.8800	0.4400	0.8800	55.00
γ -HCH	18.9200	3.9600	2.2000	2.2000	2.2000	176.00
Endosulfan I	22.3667	16.8667	8.0667	0.5500	2.9333	330.00
Endosulfan II	41.4333	36.6667	61.9667	9.9000	11.0000	319.00
HI= \sum HQ	176.0000	67.6133	81.4733	21.0100	23.6133	1353.00

Table 6: Hazard Quotients (EDI/ADI) due to water ingestion for children 30 Kg

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	WB	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α -HCH	2.2000	1.9067	0.7333	0.5867	0.2933	0.7333
β -HCH	28.3067	1.1733	2.0533	2.0533	1.9067	5.5733
δ -HCH	0.5867	0.2933	0.2933	0.1467	0.2933	0.7333
γ -HCH	6.3067	1.3200	0.7333	0.7333	0.7333	2.3467
Endosulfan I	7.4556	5.6222	2.6889	0.1833	0.9778	3.6667
Endosulfan II	13.8111	12.2222	20.6556	3.3000	3.6667	3.5444
HI= \sum HQ	58.6667	22.5378	27.1578	7.0033	7.8711	16.5978

Table 7: Hazard Quotients (EDI/ADI) due to water ingestion in adults

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	WB	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α -HCH	1.1000	0.9533	0.3667	0.2933	0.1467	0.3667
β -HCH	14.1533	0.5867	1.0267	1.0267	0.9533	2.7867
δ -HCH	0.2933	0.1467	0.1467	0.0733	0.1467	0.3667
γ -HCH	3.1533	0.6600	0.3667	0.3667	0.3667	1.1733
Endosulfan I	3.7278	2.8111	1.3444	0.0917	0.4889	1.8333
Endosulfan II	6.9056	6.1111	10.3278	1.6500	1.8333	1.7722
HI= \sum HQ	29.3333	11.2689	13.5789	3.5017	3.9356	8.2989

Carcinogenic Health Risk due to OCPs in Water

The Carcinogenic health risk is considered for all OCPs with establish cancer slope factor. The computed Cancer risk for all OCPs with established cancer slope were all greater than the range 1.0×10^{-4} to 1.0×10^{-6} recommended by US EPA.

From tables 8, 9 and 10 it can be observed that the greatest contribution to carcinogenic health risk was due to β -HCH with a range of $1.27 \times 10^{-5} - 5.28 \times 10^{-3}$. The incremental life time cancer risk ranges between $1.85 \times 10^{-1} - 4.09 \times 10^{-2}$ in a sequence Kopri > Garkida WB > Garkida > Daba > Kiri > Ndabna. The risk is inversely proportional to body weight i.e as the body weight increase the risk reduces. This can be ascribed to the fact that increase in body weight is liken to growth dilution.

Table 8: Cancer risk for water ingestion in children (10 Kg)

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	WB	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α -HCH	2.08E-01	1.80E-01	6.93E-02	5.54E-02	2.77E-02	6.93E-02
β -HCH	7.64E-01	3.17E-02	5.54E-02	5.54E-02	5.15E-02	1.50E-01
δ -HCH	1.58E-02	7.92E-03	7.92E-03	3.96E-03	7.92E-03	1.98E-02
γ -HCH	1.23E-01	2.57E-02	1.43E-02	1.43E-02	1.43E-02	4.58E-02
ILCR	1.11E+00	2.46E-01	1.47E-01	1.29E-01	1.01E-01	2.85E-01

Table 9: Cancer risk for water ingestion in children (30 Kg)

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	WB	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α -HCH	6.93E-02	6.01E-02	2.31E-02	1.85E-02	9.24E-03	2.31E-02
β -HCH	2.55E-01	1.06E-02	1.85E-02	1.85E-02	1.72E-02	5.02E-02
δ -HCH	5.28E-03	2.64E-03	2.64E-03	1.32E-03	2.64E-03	6.60E-03
γ -HCH	4.10E-02	8.58E-03	4.77E-03	4.77E-03	4.77E-03	1.53E-02
ILCR	3.70E-01	8.18E-02	4.90E-02	4.30E-02	3.38E-02	9.51E-02

Table 10: Cancer risk for water ingestion for adults

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	WB	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α -HCH	3.47E-02	3.00E-02	1.16E-02	9.24E-03	4.62E-03	1.16E-02
β -HCH	1.27E-01	5.28E-03	9.24E-03	9.24E-03	8.58E-03	2.51E-02
δ -HCH	2.64E-03	1.32E-03	1.32E-03	6.60E-04	1.32E-03	3.30E-03
γ -HCH	2.05E-02	4.29E-03	2.38E-03	2.38E-03	2.38E-03	7.63E-03
ILCR	1.85E-01	4.09E-02	2.45E-02	2.15E-02	1.69E-02	4.76E-02

Non-Carcinogenic Health Risk Hazards in Fish

Table 11, 12 and 13 shows non-carcinogenic health risk hazards in fish assessed as hazard quotients in adults, children above 30 Kg and 10Kg respectively. The HQ of OCPs due to fish consumption from all sampling location are mostly < 1 with the exception of β -HCH and endosulfan I at Ndabna, Garkida WB and Kiri. This simply implies very low probability of non-carcinogenic adverse effect with regards to OCPs due to consumption of fish except β -HCH and endosulfan I at Ndabna, Garkida WB and Kiri which indicates higher probability of adverse health effect from sampling locations.

Furthermore, HQ to due fish consumption follow the same trend with water in terms of body weight effect since as the body weight increases the HQ decreases. The HI which is the cumulative effect of the individual OCPs in fish is in the sequence Ndabna > Kiri > Garkida (WB) > Kopri > Daba > Garkida.

Table 11: Hazard Quotients (EDI/ADI) due to fish ingestion adults

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	WB	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α -HCH	0.0183	0.0134	0.0183	0.0183	0.0097	0.0243
β -HCH	0.1253	0.2884	0.2348	0.0110	0.0548	0.1290
δ -HCH	0.0122	0.0073	0.0049	0.0037	0.0073	0.0049
γ -HCH	0.0487	0.0365	0.0523	0.0195	0.0207	0.0122
Endosulfan I	0.0750	0.5840	0.0618	0.0183	0.0882	0.2971
Endosulfan II	0.1288	0.1632	0.1146	0.0548	0.0902	0.0943
HI= \sum HQ	0.4082	1.0928	0.4867	0.1253	0.2709	0.5617

Table 12: Hazard Quotients (EDI/ADI) due to fish ingestion for children (30Kg)

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	WB	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α -HCH	0.0365	0.0268	0.0365	0.0365	0.0195	0.0487
β -HCH	0.2506	0.5767	0.4696	0.0219	0.1095	0.2579
δ -HCH	0.0243	0.0146	0.0097	0.0073	0.0146	0.0097
γ -HCH	0.0973	0.0730	0.1046	0.0389	0.0414	0.0243
Endosulfan I	0.1501	1.1680	0.1237	0.0365	0.1764	0.5941
Endosulfan II	0.2575	0.3265	0.2291	0.1095	0.1805	0.1886
HI= \sum HQ	0.8164	2.1855	0.9733	0.2506	0.5418	1.1234

Table 13: Hazard Quotients (EDI/ADI) due to fish ingestion for children (10Kg)

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	WB	Garkida	Daba	kiri
α -HCH	0.1095	0.0803	0.1095	0.1095	0.0584	0.1460
β -HCH	0.7519	1.7301	1.4089	0.0657	0.3285	0.7738
δ -HCH	0.0730	0.0438	0.0292	0.0219	0.0438	0.0292
γ -HCH	0.2920	0.2190	0.3139	0.1168	0.1241	0.0730
Endosulfan I	0.4502	3.5040	0.3711	0.1095	0.5293	1.7824
Endosulfan II	0.7726	0.9794	0.6874	0.3285	0.5414	0.5658
HI= \sum HQ	2.4492	6.5566	2.9200	0.7519	1.6255	3.3702

Carcinogenic Health Risk due to OCPs in Fish

The computed Carcinogenic health risk due to fish consumption are presented in table 14, 15 and 16. From tables above the cancer risk value due to OCPs are all above the US EPA guide line recommendation. The Cumulative cancer risk which is the incremental lifetime cancer risk ranges between 8.33×10^{-4} - 3.32×10^{-3} and 5.00×10^{-3} - 1.99×10^{-2} for an Adult and a child of 10Kg weight respectively. This risk value implies that between 833 to 1990 people in a million whom are expose these pollutants may develop cancer in their life time.

Table 14: Cancer risk for fish ingestion in children (10 Kg)

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	WB	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α -HCH	3.45E-03	2.53E-03	3.45E-03	3.45E-03	1.84E-03	4.60E-03
β -HCH	6.77E-03	1.56E-02	1.27E-02	5.91E-04	2.96E-03	6.96E-03
δ -HCH	6.57E-04	3.94E-04	2.63E-04	1.97E-04	3.94E-04	2.63E-04
γ -HCH	1.90E-03	1.42E-03	2.04E-03	7.59E-04	8.07E-04	4.75E-04
ILCR	1.28E-02	1.99E-02	1.84E-02	5.00E-03	6.00E-03	1.23E-02

Table 15: Cancer risk for fish ingestion in children (30 Kg)

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	WB	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α -HCH	1.15E-03	8.43E-04	1.15E-03	1.15E-03	6.13E-04	1.53E-03
β -HCH	2.26E-03	5.19E-03	4.23E-03	1.97E-04	9.86E-04	2.32E-03
δ -HCH	2.19E-04	1.31E-04	8.76E-05	6.57E-05	1.31E-04	8.76E-05
γ -HCH	6.33E-04	4.75E-04	6.80E-04	2.53E-04	2.69E-04	1.58E-04
ILCR	4.26E-03	6.64E-03	6.14E-03	1.67E-03	2.00E-03	4.10E-03

Table 16: Cancer risk for fish ingestion in adults

OCPs	Garkida					
	Kopri	Ndabna	WB	Garkida	Daba	Kiri
α -HCH	5.75E-04	4.22E-04	5.75E-04	5.75E-04	3.07E-04	7.67E-04
β -HCH	1.13E-03	2.60E-03	2.11E-03	9.86E-05	4.93E-04	1.16E-03
δ -HCH	1.10E-04	6.57E-05	4.38E-05	3.29E-05	6.57E-05	4.38E-05
γ -HCH	3.16E-04	2.37E-04	3.40E-04	1.27E-04	1.34E-04	7.91E-05
ILCR	2.13E-03	3.32E-03	3.07E-03	8.33E-04	9.99E-04	2.05E-03

CONCLUSION

All the four isomers of HCH and endosulfan I and II were detected in water, sediments and fish samples from all the sampling locations are at concentrations above the WHO/FAO recommended MRL level of 0.01 and 0.2 mg for HCHs and endosulfans respectively. The computed health hazard in both water and fish indicate possibilities of non-carcinogenic health risk especially children because the HQ and HI decreases with increase in body weight. The carcinogenic risk computed indicates high risk of cancer from both water and fish consumption in both Adults and children with ILCR value far above the recommended 1.0×10^{-4} - 1.0×10^{-6} by USEPA.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declared no conflict in whatever form in this work.

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